

VOLTAGE LEVEL INDICATOR

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ABSTRACT

Currently, in electronics and electronics industry, great attention is paid to electronic measuring devices and their quality, reliability, compactness, ease of use, and at the same time, they are cheap. In this regard, significant positive changes are observed from year to year. Below we will consider the possibilities of electronic measuring devices and some of their inconveniences in use.

Keywords: semiconductor, diode, transistor, light-emitting diode (LED), resistor, diapason, integrated circuit, pulse, spectrum, frequency, ring.

INTRODUCTION

Electronic measuring methods and devices were invented and developed simultaneously with the emergence and development of radio engineering and electronics, and they are based on the methods of measuring electrical quantities. Electronic measurements are essential for the design, manufacture, and operation of radio, television, and radar equipment, as well as for automation, troubleshooting, computer technology, and the manufacture of electronic devices and components. Measurement methods are used in physics, chemistry, biology, medicine, geology and other scientific fields. A characteristic feature of electronic measurements is the large amount and wide ranges of measured values, such as voltage from 10^{-8} to 10^3 V, power from 10^{-16} to 10^8 W, and frequencies from 10^4 to 10^{12} Hertz. One of the most important elements used in electronic measurements is the measurement of parameters of electronic and radio components such as resistors, capacitors, inductors, semiconductor devices and integrated circuits.

Electronic measurements are carried out in the laboratory, production and normal conditions. Instruments used for laboratory measurements have high accuracy and stable parameters; they can have digital indicators of the measured quantities, or the desired position can be set with indicators and manual adjustment. Typically, electronic measurements are used to monitor and measure (with limited accuracy) various radio

equipment or environmental parameters, in particular, noise level and radiation intensity. Portable electronic counters are usually used for these purposes.

METHODS

Since we cannot see and detect electric current, that is, the movement of charged particles with our eyes, electronic measuring instruments are used to test electric current. These instruments are important for understanding the nature and voltage of electrical charges flowing in any electronic device.

A digital multimeter is a multi-purpose measuring tool widely used by technicians working in the electrical or electronics industry. It is also known as a multi-function instrument for measuring multiple units of measurement, usually Volts, Ohms and Amps. It is a handy device that can be used to test and troubleshoot electrical circuits or devices. It is used to measure the continuity, temperature, resistance, capacitance and frequency of any electrical device or electrical system or circuit.

Accuracy: Digital multimeters usually take measurements with higher accuracy than their analog counterparts. Standard analog multimeters usually measure with an accuracy of three percent, but devices with higher accuracy are also available. Standard portable digital multimeters are typically specified to have an accuracy of 0.5% over constant voltage ranges. Laboratory-grade instruments can be accurate to a few parts per million.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The production and localization of high-quality, reliable, compact and inexpensive measuring instruments is of great importance for professionals in the field of electric power, industrial electronics and similar electronic measuring instruments. In conversation with specialists in the field of electrical engineering and electronic equipment repair working in production and service organizations, most of them emphasize. As the commonly used measuring devices have many options, it is always necessary to choose the physical unit that needs to be measured, and at the same time, to choose the range of the measured value. In many cases, as a result of carelessness, incorrect selection of the physical quantity to be selected is observed and, as a result, failure of measuring instruments. So, first of all, we need to design indicators that can meet our needs and those of our colleagues.

Figure 1

Figure 1 below shows a prototype of a simple indicator that uses a resistor, a diode, a light-emitting diode and a transistor to make a circuit and display voltages up to 0.4 KV. The voltage measurement range can be changed by changing the value of resistors R1, R3, R5, R7, R9 or by increasing additional cascades, that is, it can increase or decrease to a certain value. Led emitting diode D1 shows the state of the circuit. D2, D3, D4, D5 light emitting diodes show a voltage of a certain value. For example, if the upper limit allowable voltage value is 400 volts and is configured to operate with 100 volts accuracy, LED D2 at 100 volts, LED D3 at 200 volts, LED D4 at 300 volts, LED D5 at 400 volts, ..., lights up. In order to reduce the voltage at the base of the transistor in each cascade, it is carried out using decoupling resistors. The voltage value at the base of transistor Q2 is calculated as follows. (for cascade 1) The next cascades are calculated in the same way to get the required voltage. (1-2-3 formulas)

$$V_{OUT} = V_{IN} \frac{R_2}{R_1 + R_2} \quad (1)$$

$$V_{OUT} = I_0 R_2 \quad (2)$$

$$I_0 = \frac{V_{IN}}{R_1 + R_2} \quad (3)$$

CONCLUSION

This voltage level indicator design is safe, reliable, small in size, simple in structure, and can be used without selecting the voltage value range. At the same time, the condition of the chain can be checked and it is made of cheap elements.

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